

In number of weeds in DSR, broadleaf weeds > grasses > sedges; in weed weight, grasses > broadleaf weeds > sedges. Weed weights correlated closely with rice yield, and integrated analysis indicated that grasses were the most severe problem and the predominant weed species, in spite of lower density.

The major weeds found in association with DSR and their relative density (RD)

and relative dry weight (RDW) were: grasses—*Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Eleusine indica*, and *Digitaria sanguinalis* (RD = 29.58%, RDW = 66.83%); broadleaf weeds—*Rorippa islandica* and *Portulaca oleracea* (RD = 62.75%, RDW = 25.63%); and sedges—*Cyperus rotundus* and *C. difformis* (RD = 7.67%, RDW = 7.54%).

Weeds injured the rice crop most severely 25-40 d after sowing.

Weed control recommendations for DSR farmers are to maintain the crop weed-free during the critical period; or to apply nitrofen immediately after sowing, before weed and rice seedlings emerge, then hoe weeds once within 3 wk after sowing; or hoe within 3 wk of sowing and hand weed 5 and 7 wk after sowing. ■

Integrated pest management — other pests

Comparing arthropod diversity in rice ecosystems

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Diversity reflects two common components: species richness (the number of species in a community) and species evenness or equitability. Diversity indices attempt to combine both components.

We obtained arthropod samples from five rice cultivar IR8866 cultivation sites at weekly intervals from the vegetative stage to panicle initiation. A mylar enclosure 0.5 × 0.5 × 1 m trapped all arthropods on 9 hills each.

The arthropods were sucked up using the FARMCOP suction device. Ten samples from each site were taken weekly, for a total of 540 samples. The arthropods in each sample were identified, counted, and diversity indices computed.

We used Hill's diversity numbers to describe the relationship between indices. These numbers are

Table 1. Mean values of species diversity indices for 5 rice cultivation sites in the Philippines, 1989.

Site	Mean values of diversity indices			
	N ₀	N ₁	N ₂	E ₅
Banaue	8.52	5.70	4.85	0.86
Kiangang	16.77	10.08	7.32	0.70
Bayombong	20.41	10.65	7.07	0.62
Cabanatuan	15.90	4.70	2.82	0.52
IRRI, Los Baños	30.66	12.75	8.09	0.58
LSD	2.69	1.24	0.55	0.051
F	86.8	70.2	28.5	60.6
	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
(%)	45.8	43.7	28.0	23.7

Table 2. Relative abundance of the most common arthropod species for 5 rice cultivation sites in the Philippines, 1989.

Arthropod species	Relative abundance ^a (%) in				
	Banaue	Kiangang	Bayombong	Cabanatuan	IRRI
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	12.6 ²	2.4 ⁸	8.2 ²	21.0 ²	8.9 ⁴
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	3.2	0.5	1.7	3.7 ³	1.8 ⁹
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	2.0	1.6 ¹⁰	2.6 ⁸	1.4	4.7 ⁷
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	5.9 ³	0.1	2.5 ⁹	3.5 ⁴	8.7 ⁵
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	3.3	4.8 ⁵	4.3 ⁵	2.2 ⁶	0.5
<i>Microvelia atrolineata</i>	3.3	10.9 ²	23.1 ¹	49.5 ¹	15.6 ²
<i>Mesovelia vittigera</i>	4.6 ⁵	1.8 ⁹	2.9 ⁷	0.1	1.1 ¹¹
<i>Micronecta</i> sp. 1	4.0 ⁶	0	2.1 ¹⁰	0.4	1.7 ¹⁰
<i>Micraspis</i> sp. 1	2.8	3.4 ⁷	1.9	1.5	0.2
<i>Chironomus</i> sp. 1	7.6 ⁴	7.2 ³	4.4 ⁴	0.8	16.7 ¹
<i>Smithurus</i> sp. 1	24.1 ¹	30.8 ¹	0	0	11.9 ³
Entomobryinid sp. 1	0.1	0	0	0	0.1
Staphylinidae sp. 1	0	0.1	4.9 ³	0	0
<i>Hydrellia philippina</i>	1.5	4.4 ⁶	0.5	0.5	0.1
<i>Pandosa</i> (= <i>Lycosa</i>) <i>pseudoannulata</i>	2.7	5.3 ⁴	3.1 ⁶	2.1	2.9 ⁸
<i>Tetragnatha maxillosa</i>	0.6	2.1	1.7	0.7	2.9 ⁸
<i>Atypena</i> (= <i>Callitrichia</i>) <i>formosana</i>	0.3	1.1	2.9 ⁷	2.3 ⁵	5.5 ⁶
Very abundant species (no.)	5	7	7	3	8
Abundant species (no.)	6	10	11	5	12
% contribution of abundant species	58.8	73.1	60.0	80.0	82.4
Total arthropods, N	5811	11321	8294	15500	21849

^aNumbers in superscript represent ranking of relative abundance.

$$N_0 = S \quad (1) \quad \text{chosen at random from a collection of } S \text{ species and } N \text{ individuals will belong.}$$

where S is the total number of species. Thus, Hill's diversity number N₁ measures the number of abundant species in a sample. H¹ is defined as

$$N_1 = e^H \quad (2) \quad H^1 = \sum_{i=1}^S (p_i / \ln p_i) \quad (4)$$

where H is Shannon's index, and

$$N_2 = 1/h \quad (3)$$

where h is Simpson's index

Shannon's index (H¹) is based on information theory. It measures the average degree of uncertainty in predicting to what species an individual

where S is the number of species and p_i is the proportion of the total number of individuals in the ith species.

Simpson's index is defined as

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^S p_i^2 \quad (5)$$

where p_i is the proportional abundance of the i^{th} species. Thus N_2 is the number of very abundant species.

For evenness,

$$E5 = \frac{N_2 - 1}{N_1 - 1} \quad (6)$$

is appropriate, since E5 will approach zero when a single species is most dominant.

Diversity was lowest in Cabanatuan, followed by Banaue; IRRI farm had the highest diversity (Table 1).

The units of indices N_0 , N_1 , and N_2 are in numbers of species, representing the number of species in the samples (species richness), abundant species, and very abundant species, respectively. In Cabanatuan, where N_1 was 4.70, five species accounted for 80% of the abundance (Table 2). In Banaue, six

species accounted for 59% of the abundance. On IRRI farm, eight very abundant species accounted for 75% of the abundance.

A total of 240 species were found at the five sites. Because the sampling procedure was constant, N_0 , the total number of species in the community or species richness, may be used for comparison. IRRI farm was significantly "richer" in arthropod species than other sites (Table 1); Banaue was the "poorest." The sites differed significantly, with Banaue having the highest mean value. In general, E5 is sensitive to the number of species in a sample, which probably accounts for the lower means in IRRI and Cabanatuan. Similarities between Banaue and Kiangnan may be related to co-dominance of *Smithurus* sp.; for Bayombong, Cabanatuan, and IRRI, co-dominance by

Microvelia atrolineata may have played an important role.

Cabanatuan had the lowest diversity (as determined by N_1 , N_2 , and E5). However, its species richness (N_0) is almost twice that of Banaue. Five species accounted for 80% of all arthropods in Cabanatuan: in Banaue, it required more than 16 species to account for 80%. Lower arthropod densities in Banaue are probably a result of lower ambient temperatures due to elevation; Banaue is 1,524 m above sea level; Cabanatuan, 61 m.

However, elevation does not appear to be the only factor affecting arthropod diversity. IRRI has an elevation of 22 m above sea level, but has the highest diversity. The greater diversity in germplasm and plant stages on the IRRI farm may have accounted for this difference. ■

Farming systems

Survival of rice stem borer (SB) in different cropping systems in Sindh

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Rice in Sindh is grown in two distinct tracts: Lower Sindh and Upper Sindh. Among rice pests, the yellow SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* is predominant. Larvae hibernate in rice stubbles during winter (Nov-Mar) and emerge as adults in mid-Mar, depending on environmental conditions.

An extensive survey in Jan 1988 examined the carryover of SB in different rice-based cropping systems. SB incidence, larval population, and larval mortality were measured in seven cropping systems at 20 locations in Lower Sindh and 33 in Upper Sindh. The stubbles of 50 rice hills were randomly collected in each field. Similar observations were made in no-tillage and conventional tillage wheat fields at four locations in Upper Sindh.

Data show that of 1,260 larvae collected in both tracts, 1,182 (98%)

were *Scirpophaga* and only 24 (2%) were *Sesamia* (Table 1). Overall mortality was higher in Lower Sindh (56%) than in Upper Sindh (34%). Number of live larvae per 50 stubbles and tiller infestation were higher in Upper Sindh. Low larval mortality in

lathyrus may be due to crop canopy shading the stubbles. Larval mortality was low in ricefields that were not properly plowed, and where stubbles were not fully uprooted. Mortality was higher in fields that were properly prepared and left fallow.

Table 1. Survival of SB larvae in cropping systems in Lower and Upper Sindh, India.

Cropping system	Larval density (no./50 stubbles)				Mortality (%)	Tiller infestation (%)
	<i>Scirpophaga</i>		Live <i>Sesamia</i> ^a			
	Live	Dead				
	<i>Lower Sindh</i> ^b					
Fallow (unplowed)	35	11	3		22	32.92
Fallow (plowed)	12	31	—		72	28.94
Berseem	19	23	4		50	28.49
Wheat/barley	15	30	2		64	24.92
Lentil	13	15	—		54	18.01
Mustard (plowed)	4	9	—		69	12.89
Sugarcane	9	14	—		61	17.03
Mean	15	19	1		56	23.31
	<i>Upper Sindh</i> ^c					
Fallow (unplowed)	41	10	4		18	49.34
Fallow (plowed)	6	21	2		72	18.39
Berseem	16	9	3		32	15.34
Wheat	29	21	5		38	26.27
Lathyrus (unplowed)	92	22	—		19	38.12
Mustard (unplowed)	15	1	—		6	22.65
Chickpea	10	11	1		50	23.71
Mean	30	14	2		34	27.68

^aNo dead *Sesamia* ^bMean of 20 locations. ^cMean of 33 locations.